

LRP2020 White Paper on Industrial Initiatives in Canadian Astronomy

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1 Background: “State of R&D in Canada” Report (2018)

In 2017, an expert panel was convened by the Council of Canadian Academies¹ in response to a request from the Minister of Science. Their charge was to review the State of Science and Technology and Industrial Research and Development in Canada. A report was prepared for the Government of Canada, on “*Competing in a Global Innovation Economy: The Current State of R&D in Canada*”²

The executive summary of this Report notes that “national prosperity, competitiveness, and well-being are inextricably linked to the capacity to participate in and benefit from research, development, and innovation”. Thus, the Report provides an assessment of the latest evidence of Canada’s R&D and innovation performance, combining up-to-date data on research output, impact, and strength across all disciplines, with expert insights and analyses, and bench-marking against the performance of other countries.

In the Report, “Canada’s Average Relative Citation (ARC) rank in 2009–2014 remained unchanged at sixth place from 2003 to 2008. Canada’s research reputation also remained unchanged at fourth place, according to a survey of top-cited researchers from around the world.” But more specifically, Canada ranks among the top five countries in Psychology and Cognitive Sciences, Clinical Medicine, Physics and Astronomy, Historical Studies, and Visual and Performing Arts. And in particular, the subfield of Astronomy & Astrophysics was ranked “much higher than the other subfields” in Physics & Astronomy - in fact, Canadian Astronomy & Astrophysics was listed as in the Top 1% in the world, and was the only STEM field in Canada to be so highly ranked.

Overall, Astronomy & Astrophysics is recognized by the Canadian government to be of the highest quality and to have the potential to be a substantial R&D driver. This has been a core principle at the National Research Council, where astronomers at the Herzberg Astronomy & Astrophysics Research Centre (NRC-HAA) have many opportunities to work closely with engineers and industry partners. However, it is more difficult for the typical astronomer working at a Canadian university to connect to researchers in industry. Thus, in this white paper, we attempt to summarize existing and innovative ways in which Canadian research astronomers are working with Canadian industry partners, and prospects for the near future.

2 Current Industrial Engagement in Canadian Astronomy

Most engagement between the Canadian astronomical research community (e.g., as represented by the CASCA Long Range Plan) and Canadian industry is organized through or directly involves the NRC-HAA. At NRC-HAA, Canadians have the resources and expertise for significant, and increasingly international, design, management, and planning efforts. Also NRC-HAA strategically provides support for projects led by Canadian university researchers who engage with industry, thereby enhancing the opportunities, providing expert management, and helping to mitigate risks.

However, it is important to note that significant astronomical instrumentation has been carried out in Canada without NRC-HAA involvement, e.g., CFHT/SITELLE (ABB) and some space missions (MOST, BRITe). Many

¹The Council of Canadian Academies is an independent, not-for-profit organization that supports independent, science-based, authoritative expert assessments to inform public policy development in Canada. It is supported by its three founding Member Academies - The Royal Society of Canada, The Canadian Academy of Engineering, and The Canadian Academy of Health Sciences.

²Council of Canadian Academies, 2018. *Competing in a Global Innovation Economy: The Current State of R&D in Canada*. Ottawa (ON): Expert Panel on the State of Science and Technology and Industrial Research and Development in Canada, Council of Canadian Academies. Available at http://new-report.scienceadvice.ca/assets/report/Competing_in_a_Global_Innovation_Economy_FullReport_EN.pdf

instrumentation competencies overlap with industry, however as NRC-HAA has a deep understanding of Canada's astronomy infrastructure and a close relationship with its observatories, it is ideally positioned to facilitate between industrial capabilities and observatory and instrumentation project needs. The current model often sees NRC-HAA providing a leadership role, including science and system level technical knowledge, while industry is contracted for critical components, sub-assemblies or key industrial competencies. This differs from the Canadian Space Agency which does not have in house technical or astronomical science expertise.

2.1 National Research Council -Herzberg Astronomy & Astrophysics (NRC-HAA)

In providing astronomical research facilities for Canadians, NRC-HAA often partners with Canadian universities and industry. These facilities can be initiated in several ways, including directly by NRC-HAA, often following prioritization in the CASCA Long Range Plan; through initiatives at observatories in which Canada has an ownership stake; or by university researcher funded programs (e.g., CFI projects) where the PI has sought NRC-HAA partnership.

Industrial partnerships are increasingly important as facilities and instrumentation projects increase in scale. A first example of this was the ALMA Band 3 receivers project involving Daniels Electronics (Victoria, BC) and Nanowave (Etobicoke, ON), completed in 2014³. For the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) Project, development of instrumentation and the observatory enclosure has involved industrial partnerships with Dynamic Structures (Port Coquitlam, BC), Sightline Engineering (Victoria, BC), and ABB, INO and OMP (all in Quebec City, QC). *It is worth noting that industrial involvement was mandated with the federal funding commitment to TMT, which has played an important role in developing Canadian industry partnerships.* For the Square Kilometre Array (SKA), NRC-HAA has partnered with MDA (Vancouver, BC) in the pre-construction development of the Correlator System. Additionally, NRC-HAA is involving industry in the early development phases of the ngVLA project.

Other proposed projects that will certainly require significant industrial collaborations include: CASTOR (the Cosmological Advanced Survey Telescope for Optical and uv Research, a proposed Canadian Space Agency satellite mission), MSE (the Maunakea Spectroscopic Explorer, a proposed upgrade of the CFHT to an 11-m telescope focused on dedicated spectroscopic surveys), and CHORD (the Canadian Hydrogen Observatory and Radio-transient Detector, a proposed next-generation radio telescope).

2.2 Canadian Space Agency

No comments at this time (see CASTOR comment in the previous paragraph).

2.3 Engagement with Canadian Industries

In Table 1, we have compiled a list of Canadian industry partners who are engaged in significant astronomy-related research and astronomical instrumentation projects. In making this list, we tried to identify industries which are more than just vendors, i.e., those that have played a significant role in the design, fabrication, testing, etc., of current and recent astronomical instrumentation.

Furthermore, the goal in making this list is to identify and highlight the many options for students trained in astronomy to continue to work in astronomical research through industry. This option is nearly non-existent in the typical astronomy graduate curricula at Canadian universities, and one of the purposes (and value-added components) of the current NSERC CREATE training programs.

3 NSERC CREATE Training Programs

The Program: The NSERC Collaborative Research and Training Experience (CREATE) program encourages collaborative and integrative training approaches to address significant scientific challenges associated with Canada's

³S. Claude et al. 2014, Journal of Infrared, Millimeter, and Terahertz Waves, Vol. 35, p. 563; <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10762-014-0071-2>

research priorities. This includes facilitating the transition of new researchers from trainees to productive employees in the Canadian workforce, and improving their job-readiness for careers in industry, government, non-governmental organizations, and/or academia. Therefore, NSERC seeks CREATE training programs that increase collaboration between industry and academia, particularly in research areas considered a Canadian strength and high impact (e.g., Astronomy & Astrophysics, as cited in the 2018 Report on the State of R&D in Canada above). The total funding is \$1.65M over 6 years, where 80% of these CREATE funds must be spent on student trainee stipends.

Industrial-Stream: The CREATE program includes an industrial-stream track to further support improved job-readiness within the industrial sector by exposing participants to the specific challenges and opportunities of this sector and training people with skills identified by industry. NSERC expects the industrial-stream programs to contribute to Canada's "People Advantage" by increasing the number of highly qualified personnel (HQP) who are "employer-ready" and who can generate immediate results after graduation, providing an immediate benefit to industrial employers.

Lesson learned: NSERC looks very favourably on CREATE programs that are industrial-stream. Currently, their website says "up to 50% of the CREATE grants will be dedicated to the industrial stream". In the past, it was a much higher fraction. Nevertheless, all successful programs are expected to be closely coupled to industrial research programs, and therefore it is important to have several industry partners involved in the original proposal.

Professional Skills Courses: CREATE Programs do not have to develop new professional skills training courses, as they can take advantage of existing training courses (offered at academic institutions, or by other organizations such as Mitacs). Recently, "NSERC and Mitacs have formalized their existing relationship. Applicants are encouraged to take advantage of Mitacs programs that support internships in industry as well as other opportunities to increase the number of trainees."

Lesson learned: Mitacs programs are amazing and we should all be taking their professional skills workshops. These are offered across Canada, they are free to students and staff, and some are even offered as online courses. But the timing is specified by Mitacs, so one has to schedule around them. This is an easy requirement to fulfill, but students must be proactive about signing up for these.

Value-added Training: The CREATE program training initiative is intended to focus on providing an enriched training experience for **graduate students** (master's and doctoral). Undergraduate students can be supported and integrated into the training program as potential future graduate students. Postdocs (PDFs) are also permitted, but need to be fully justified in terms of their relevance to the program goals, e.g., collaborations with industry.

Lesson learned: Industry do alot of interesting research in instrumentation, and really do things differently from university or government labs, so the industrial internships are critical to these objectives and extremely valuable experiences no matter what trainees do later.

Proactive Recruitment of Women: NSERC is acting on the evidence that equity, diversity and inclusion strengthen the scientific and engineering communities and the quality, social relevance and impact of research. CREATE initiatives are expected to increase the inclusion and advancement of under-represented and disadvantaged groups in the natural sciences and engineering as one way to enhance excellence in research and training.

Lesson learned: It can be difficult to find women applicants for these programs, and proactive recruiting is encouraged (or necessary).

3.1 TEPS (2015)

The NSERC CREATE training program in Technologies for Exoplanetary Science (TEPS) was established in 2015 and addresses the primary objectives of the CREATE program by offering students and PDFs innovative and collaborative learning environments, and can include internships, student mobility, and professional training. This is not an industrial-stream CREATE program.

TEPS is motivated by the fact that we live in a remarkable age when hundreds of new planets are being discovered every year, rewriting our understanding of the Universe and our place within it. Their discovery is dependent on innovative new technologies in robotics, aerospace, remote sensing, adaptive optics, and spectroscopy, requiring scientists to work together with engineers and industry partners. These technologies build on Canada's past

advances, will drive new innovation and economic growth, and will enable the major new discoveries of tomorrow.

Canada has played a leading role in both exoplanetary astronomy and solar system science, using space-borne and ground-based tools. Signature technologies have raised Canada's stature, and with upcoming commitments to new instruments the demand for HQP in aerospace and robotics continues to grow. The TEPS program aims to enhance Canada's human resource, science, and technological capabilities, helping to secure Canada's leadership position in space science and technology, as well as advanced optical and infrared instrumentation.

Lessons learned: it is much easier to convince graduate students to spend time abroad than to spend time in industry. As such the international internship component of TEPS has been very popular while the industrial internships can still be counted on one hand. At the MSc level this is unsurprising: the time frame at many Canadian institutions makes it effectively impossible to spend 4 months off campus as an industrial intern. At the PhD level, there is still some reticence—both among students and their supervisors—to spend a substantial amount of time working on something other than their science thesis, despite monetary compensation and the well-known statistics showing that most PhDs will go on to real-world jobs. Since TEPS is not an industrial-stream CREATE, this has not been an existential threat. Nonetheless, it shows that there is still much work to do in bridging the culture gap between academia and industry.

3.2 NTCO (2017)

The NSERC CREATE training program in New Technologies for Canadian Observatories (NTCO) is an industrial-stream program established in 2017. NTCO is designed to better prepare students for leadership in Canadian astronomy and high-tech industry, while also helping to generate industrial initiatives within Canada. NTCO aims to elevate Canada's global position in emerging instrumentation technologies, helping to maximize Canadian investments in multi-national ground-based, space-based, remote-orbiting, and space-cruising observatories.

The NTCO team includes researchers from 10 universities, three observatories, two government labs, one astronomy Institute, and over a dozen Canadian industries. Students are provided with unique, hands-on experience in instrumentation technologies, something that is lacking in the standard graduate curriculum. The NTCO program is further enhanced by professional skills training workshops, annual team meetings, co-supervision of all trainees, an integrated thesis or dissertation, and participation in the Dunlap Institute Instrumentation Summer School (and/or equivalent). The program typically has 20-25 student participants per year from across Canada.

Lessons learned: (1) While this program was designed around four themes (detectors, optics & photonics, focal plane technologies, and manufacturing), about one third of the students and about one third of the industrial partners/internships are interested in instrumentation-related software development, particularly machine-learning application (some of this is captured in the LRP White Paper on Machine Learning). (2) As discussed above for the TEPS program, the industrial internship requirement is a challenge. Industry find that the 2-month minimum for undergrads is usually too short (this is to ensure undergrads also work in the university or government environment too), and graduate students find that 4 to 6-month internships are difficult to fulfill while doing their thesis or dissertation research. To overcome this challenge, students need to identify a likely internship on their applications, approved by their co-supervisors, but then the co-supervisors are warned that if the internship does not materialize, then they must return the funding to the program. Lastly, we have yet to identify an appropriate PDF industrial-stream internship/NTCO opportunity. (3) The NTCO program has had a very difficult time attracting women student applicants (so far, though we meet and exceed targets from other under represented groups). The NTCO team are exploring new ways to aggressively recruit women students, and reaching out to individuals in the astronomy and engineering communities.

3.3 Other CREATE Proposals

Other members of the Canadian astronomy community have developed CREATE training program proposals that were supported by their universities, but were not selected for funding by the CREATE program. NSERC receives ~50 CREATE proposals per year, and selects ~15; thus, less than a 3:1 success rate. However, this follows a severe down-select process at each university also, estimated as over 3:1. Thus in total, about 15 are funded per

150 proposals sent to the universities each year, which covers all NSERC-supported fields of research.

One of these unfunded proposals is ‘StarTrain’, an astronomy-related, industrial-stream proposal, led by Western University with participation from nine other universities. Their aim was to link Canadian university astrophysics research groups with Canadian technology-based startup companies. Tech startups require talented staff with scarce data analytic skill sets to fuel innovation and economic growth. Astrophysics trainees represent an untapped, diverse talent source for a wide range of topics in data science and analytics: connecting startups and astrophysics HQP would benefit both groups. Astrophysics training already develops skills in programming, analytics, modeling, and communication; and through the StarTrain program, the goal was that HQP would also gain exposure to entrepreneurship and networking, additional technical skills, and critical ‘foot-in-the-door’ work experience.

Lessons learned: Feedback from NSERC LOI reviews to date implies that non-astronomer academics are unconvinced about the transferrability of astronomy HQPs’ data analytics skills. This is not true of industrial colleagues who supported the proposal! A ‘proof-of-concept’ program might help.

4 Other Opportunities for Academic Engagement with Industry

4.1 Canadian Foundation for Innovation (CFI)

CFI makes financial contributions to Canada’s universities, colleges, research hospitals, and non-profit research organizations to increase their capability to carry out high-quality research. The Innovation Fund (described below, formerly *Leading Edge Fund*) has played a critical role in Canadian astronomy over the past decade, in providing substantial funding for key astronomical instrumentation projects and driving key partnerships with Canadian industry. These have included ;

- VLOT (< 2005, PI Ray Carlberg, UofT)
- Canadian VLBI (< 2005, PI Ue-Li Pen, UofT)
- RAVEN (< 2005, PI Colin Bradley, UVic)
- OMM (2009, PI Rene Doyon, Udm)
- CHIME (2012, PI Marc Halpern, UBC)
- CHIME-FRB (2015, PI Vicky Kaspi, McGill)
- SPIROU/NIRPS (2015, PI Rene Doyon, Udm)
- CIRADA (2017, PI Bryan Gaensler, UofT)
- GIRMOS (2017, PI Suresh Sivanandam, UofT)
- CGEM (2017, PI Gary Hinshaw, UBC)

4.1.1 Innovation Fund

The Innovation Fund provides investments in infrastructure, across the full spectrum of research, from the most fundamental to applied through to technology development. As stated on their website, “The CFI invests in infrastructure that researchers need to think big, innovate, and push the boundaries of knowledge.” The CFI defines an institutional envelope as the upper limit on the total value of funding that an eligible institution may request. It is based on the average share of research funding that the institution received from the three federal research-funding agencies over the previous 3-4 years. Eligible institutions without an envelope receive a starting envelope of \$1.75M. Multi institutional projects are defined as those that bring together three or more CFI-eligible collaborating institutions and that will house part of the infrastructure or pool resources; an additional 5% of the CFI award may be requested to cover administrative costs associated with the management and governance of those projects.

In the 2020 competition⁴, the CFI will invest up to \$400M in research infrastructure funding and will fund up to 40% of a project's eligible infrastructure costs. The CFI will provide up to \$120M for associated operating costs through the Infrastructure Operating Fund. An eligible project involves acquiring or developing research infrastructure to both increase research capacity and support world-class research. Construction costs to build new space or to renovate existing space are eligible.

Note: Proposals may include advanced research computing infrastructure and related resources to carry out a research or technology development project. However, proposals that focus predominantly on major, collective and shared advanced research computing infrastructure will not be accepted in the 2020 competition. These advanced research computing needs will be covered by and addressed through the national Digital Research Infrastructure⁵ strategy announced by Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada in April 2019.

4.1.2 Other CFI Programs

Other CFI programs can also provide funding for infrastructure and are worth keeping in mind for industry partnerships in astronomy-related research. As of January 2020, these are;

- *Exceptional Opportunities Fund* : This program is for the very few instances when an exceptional research opportunity would be missed if a project had to wait to undergo the normal course of a national competition. It must take advantage of an exceptional and time-sensitive opportunity and partnership that justifies having the project considered outside the normal pan-Canadian competitive review process. This fund has not been used for astronomy-related research (yet).
- *College-Industry Innovation Fund* : This program is intended to support substantial research infrastructure projects that will augment the existing applied research and technology development capacity of colleges, and allow them to respond to important sector industry needs. Colleges can submit up to two (independent) proposals per competition under each stream of the CIIF and request up to \$1 million per proposal from the CFI. This fund has not been used for astronomy-related research (yet).
- *John R. Evans Leaders Fund (JELF)* : JELF funding is for research infrastructure to individual researchers and institutions. Universities can request up to \$800K from the CFI, with a maximum total eligible cost of \$2M. Several Canadian astronomers have received JELF funding (typically < \$100K). These do not require an industrial partnership but they do require matching funds that can come from industry.
- *Canada Research Chairs Infrastructure Fund* : this program has contributed substantially to Canadian astronomy infrastructure at the universities over the past 20 years. Several Canadian astronomers have received this funding (typically < \$250K), but these do not require an industrial partnership.
- *Major Science Initiatives Fund* : now closed.
- *Cyberinfrastructure Initiative* : now closed.

4.2 Mitacs

Mathematics of Information Technology and Complex Systems (Mitacs) is a nonprofit national research organization that, in partnerships with Canadian academia, private industry, and government, operates research and training programs in fields related to industrial and social innovation. Mitacs are an effective link between industry and post-secondary institutions, driving collaborations at home and abroad to develop projects which solve business challenges, and develop the nation's innovation capacity

Mitacs offers many wonderful programs that astronomers and industry partners really should be more aware of and use more often. They are a very effective way to find, fund, and share talent, and their Training Programs

⁴The CFI Innovation Fund 2020 Call for Proposals is available at :

https://www.innovation.ca/sites/default/files/Funds/IF/2020innovationfund_call_for_proposalsv02.pdf

⁵For more information see: <https://www.ic.gc.ca/eic/site/136.nsf/eng/home>

(see below) are seriously great! Furthermore, each university/Province has a Mitacs Coordinator who can help with navigating the Mitacs application processes and answer questions. Mitacs programs in 2020 include ;

- *Accelerate (PDFs)* : This program provides funding for postdocs to have an internship at an organization that “needs their expertise”. This includes eligible businesses and not-for-profit organizations operating in Canada, for-profit businesses operating outside of Canada, and eligible intern-owned start-ups at approved incubators. Funding starts at \$15,000, with a financial contribution starting at \$7,500 from the organization. The expectation is that the postdoc will spend approximately 50% of the internship with the university and 50% with the partner organization.
- *Elevate (PDFs)* : Establish long-term collaborations between university researchers and industry partners through this program, which will fund postdoctoral researcher for up to two years (up to \$120,000), with an industry partner contribution (starting at \$30,000). This program includes management skills and career development training.
- *Globalink (students)* : Funding for international research exchanges for undergraduate and graduate students (typically 16-24 week projects). Mitacs helps by evaluating the student academic records, helping to convert grades to a common scale for easier comparisons (this can be a big help), and supports the Globalink students with a local contact who can help students adjust to their new environments and culture. University researchers and industry partners are eligible hosts for these students. However, Globalink offers two-way mobility, funding both the student stipends and travel costs for research at universities, whereas industry partners are expected to provide matching funds starting at \$7500 for a 16-24 week project.
- *Training Programs (students & PDFs)* : Mitacs Training programs provide professional skills development courses for graduate students and postdoctoral fellows. The courses are designed to complement the hands-on research skills and experience gained by participants of Mitacs programs such as Accelerate, Elevate, and Globalink. Each course is designed to improve upon one or more core competencies and is facilitated by industry leaders. Courses are offered in all 10 provinces **and online**, they are available throughout the year, and they are open to graduate students, postdoctoral fellows, and Mitacs program participants. Seriously, these are great!
- *Entrepreneur International (travel grants)*: this program offers matching funds for travel grants to Canadian start-ups housed in university-linked incubators. The funds are to connect with international incubators, allowing individuals to explore new business development opportunities in global markets.
- *Canadian Science Policy Fellowship (PDFs)* : this program offers PhD holders from all disciplines a 12-month immersion into the policy making process with participating government departments.

4.3 NSERC Alliance Grants

As of 2019, the new NSERC Alliance grants program replaces a number of programs that have been used to partner with industry for astronomy-related research. These include the Industrial Research Chairs (IRC), the Collaborative Research and Development grants (CRD), the Engage/Engage Plus grants, the Connect grants, and the Strategic Networks grants. Some astronomical applications of these older programs are described below. The new Alliance grants support projects of varying scale and complexity, from small individual research projects to long-term projects involving researchers across several universities and/or partner organizations across multiple sectors. At least one of these partners must have a demonstrated ability to exploit research results (i.e., demonstrate its ability either to perform R&D relevant to this project or to apply its results directly), while other partners may be chosen for their ability to generate and mobilize knowledge, and all partner organizations must collectively support the project through cash and/or in-kind contributions.

Today, the Alliance grants come in two Options (1 & 2), depending on the size and duration of the project and industry partner(s). In Option 1, grants between \$20K and \$1M per year are available for projects from 1-5 years

duration; in Option 2, grants between \$20K and \$200K are available also for projects from 1-5 years duration. The percentage of the research project funding to be covered by an Alliance grant depends on the cost-sharing⁶ with industry partners, using a detailed formula that depends on the size and type of industry partner organization(s) involved. COM DEV and ABB have both commented that they were not heavy users of these NSERC programs in the past; however, they were disappointed by the first phase of these new Alliance grants, which include a much higher industry buy-in. They are hopeful that the next phase of the Alliance grants will require a lower cost-sharing threshold for companies like theirs.

The following are a few notes on how the former NSERC programs were used by some university researchers and industrial partners in the past ~5 years (*this list is likely to be incomplete*) :

- *Industrial Research Chairs (IRC, < 2019)*: Prof. Simon Thibault has held an IRC in Optical Design at Laval since 2008, in collaboration with INO (Institut National d’Optics, in Quebec City). Prof. Rene Doyon also held an IRC in space industries at Udm (<2010), in collaboration with the Canada Space Agency. *Lessons learned: There was a significant cost-sharing requirement for industry partners with these positions, and therefore it was important that industry see direct benefits.*
- *Collaborative Research and Development (CRD, < 2019)* : In 2012, Honeywell/COMDEV had a CRD grant with Prof. Matt Dobbs (McGill) to jumpstart their work on the LiteBIRD satellite. They also had a large CRD with UGuelph to look at Advanced Life Support systems for (manned) space exploration (not specifically astronomy, but aligned with the TEPS CREATE program).
- *Engage/Engage Plus (< 2019)* : COM DEV participated in one of the last Engage grants with Prof. Scott Chapman (NRC-HAA/Dalhousie/UBC/) to examine some detector characterization for a possible future project on optical inter satellite links.
- *Connect (< 2019)* : Profs. Sarah Gallagher and Kim Venn received funding through the Connect program for a 1-day industry-graduate student event at CASCA2018. *Lessons learned: Connect funding could be really helpful, but regional, and applicants had to know to contact their regional NSERC office well in advance of an event. While this program has been absorbed into the Alliance grants, the current Alliance funding Options are not similar to the old Connect grants, so this source seems to have disappeared.*
- *Strategic Projects and Networks* : No known examples.

4.4 Industrial Problem Solving Workshops / Industrial Short Courses

The Pacific Institute for the Mathematical Sciences (PIMS) began *Industrial Problem Solving Workshops* (IPSWs) in Canada over 20 years ago. With funding from NSERC, the IPSW aim to create mutually beneficial links between industrial researchers and their counterparts in academia, with a focus on mathematical, statistical, and computational problems that arise in real industrial setting. In the most recent IPSW (Montreal 2019)⁷, researchers at the NRC-DRAO submitted a problem for the workshop on “Automatically identifying patterns and novel behaviours in the radio-frequency environment at DRAO” and it was selected as one of nine other (unrelated) problems for the workshop. Over the course of the 5-day workshop, researchers at NRC-DRAO presented their technical problem, and leading specialists from the academic community studied these problems in small teams, then present a summary the results at the end of the week. The teams also prepare complete reports for delivery to the industrial sponsors.

Lessons Learned: NRC-DRAO participants in the 2019 IPSW in Montreal commented that this is a great opportunity for young astronomers to work with industry without a huge commitment on either side. This workshop produced new contacts in academia (astronomical and otherwise) and in industry, and was “a ridiculously positive experience for all concerned”.

⁶Details on the cost-sharing amounts for the NSERC Alliance grants, Options 1 and 2, are described here: https://www.nserc-sng.gc.ca/Innovate-Innover/alliance-alliance/funding-financement_eng.asp

⁷ISWP 2019, see <http://www.crm.umontreal.ca/probindustriels/?lang=en>

The IPSW programs happen annually⁸. PIMS now takes turns in organizing the IPSW as national workshops with CRM (Centre de recherches mathématiques, Montreal) and the Fields Institute (Toronto).

PIMS also offers *Industrial Short Courses* with topics of interest to both industry and academia. As industry scientists have a desire to stay in contact with current research being carried out at the universities, and academics are constantly looking for relevant “real-life” problems, the PIMS Industrial Short Courses seek to bridge the two parties. No examples related to astronomy were found for this report.

4.5 Private Funding

Private funding sources is a common way to fund big science throughout the world, and yet has not had a long tradition in astronomy in Canada. The only example found for this report is private funding through the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation in the US for the CHIME outriggers. This funding is to be used for the planning and preparation stages to build “outrigger” telescopes for CHIME in various parts of North America, to help pinpoint the location of Fast Radio Bursts and identify their origins. This funding was awarded to Prof. Vicky Kaspi and the McGill Space Institute, which is also partially supported by private funding from the Trottier Family Foundation.

4.6 Provincial Incentive Programs

Provincial support for astronomy is often provided through matching funds to successful CFI grants. Provinces are certainly interested in supporting industrial innovation and partnerships across Canada. There may be other Provincial programs and incentives for astronomy researchers in academia and government to partner with local industries, but we found no examples in astronomy found for this report.

5 Additional Comments

5.1 Programming Skills, Platforms, and Industry

“Big Data”, “Machine Learning”, and programming skills and platforms in general, have been rapidly developing over the past decade, at a pace that is too fast for non-software related Canadian industries. And yet, modern programming skills have become an essential tool for scientific progress, underpinning world-class research across all disciplines, including astronomy, and in industry. One of the most valuable skills that graduate students in astronomy develop is a familiarity and comfort with the most current software programs, platforms, and customs.

National Research Council: The NRC’s world-class scientists are an important part of the Canadian Government’s strategy to help to advance Canadian academia and industry. Their facilities, expertise, networks and stable commitment help to convene strategic, large-scale national teams committed to innovation. Budget 2018 helped to lower the cost of partnering with the NRC so more small and medium-sized industries, colleges, and universities are able to make use of its services. In astronomy software and data, the Canadian Astronomical Data Centre (CADC) lead this NRC effort, including the development of the Canadian Advanced Network For Astronomy Research (CANFAR). Through CANFAR (operated by NRC’s CADC), astronomers in Canada have direct and easy access to cyber infrastructure, growing numbers of GPUs, fast access to resources, fast and interactive processing, and safe storage. Furthermore, NRC-HAA CADC are a working model of the value and innovation possible when expertise is brought together from computer science, engineering, data science, focused on astronomy. Students working within the CANFAR ecosystem become expert in industry standard processes for computing and data analytics. The CANFAR platform provides an opportunity to expand astronomy’s Canadian industry partners.

AI Research Institutions (MILA, Vector, AMII): Canada is home to the world-leading AI research centers: the Montreal Institute for Learning Algorithms (MILA, Montreal), the Vector Institute for Artificial Intelligence (Vector, Toronto), and the Alberta Machine Intelligence Institute (AMII, Edmonton). These are not-for-profit

⁸A list of IPSWs over the past decade can be found here : http://www.crm.umontreal.ca/act/programme/progARPI-IPSW_an.shtml.

research and educational institutions, closely partnered with the universities, and partially supported through government funding. MILA and Vector were founded in 2017, while AMII has a 15 year history. All of these institutions work with industry, start-ups, incubators, and accelerators to advance AI research and drive its application, adoption, and commercialization across Canada. Links with these specialized institutions can provide Canadian astronomers and industry partners with a competitive advantage in the era of big data science. One example may be to embed machine learning applications into the next generation of Canadian astronomical instrumentation (e.g., TMT-IRMOS) and/or surveys (MSE). There could also be excellent opportunities for collaborations with industry on autonomous telescopes, which are a lot less dangerous than autonomous vehicles. Furthermore, this new programming technique is known to draw top students and researchers from interdisciplinary fields, such that astronomy graduate students with opportunities to work with ML/AI provide an ideal link with Canadian industry.

Additionally, the BC provincial government have recently committed \$17M over the next five years to establish a new *Quantum Algorithms Institute* in Vancouver, BC (at Simon Fraser University's Surrey campus). The institute's mission is to engage researchers, staff, and students with local communities and industry partners to solve societal challenges through innovation and entrepreneurship.

5.2 Sample Comments & Information from Industry Partners

COM DEV (*courtesy Neil Rowlands*): COM DEV Ltd (doing business as Honeywell) maintains a thriving aerospace export business, having supplied communications hardware to the global satellite industry for the past 40 years. Currently 80% of all operational satellites carry COM DEV equipment; all designed, built and tested in our Cambridge, ON facility. COM DEV has also supplied the majority of the optical and space science instrumentation that the Canadian Space Agency has flown in the last few decades. Our business is highly technical; of our 800 Canadian employees, over 100 have advanced degrees. The telecommunications industry is constantly evolving and in order to maintain our competitive advantage we must strive to continually enhance our skills set, something which can only be done by recruiting the best and brightest highly qualified personnel. We have found that graduates from programs in astronomical instrumentation, computation and big data surveys typically have a broad base of skills and have a unique ability to “see the big picture”, in that they are able to contribute to company issues well beyond their immediate tasks. A number of such graduates have become leaders in our technical staff.

MDA (*from website*): MDA develops and delivers advanced surveillance and intelligence solutions, defence and maritime systems, radar geospatial imagery, space robotics, satellite antennas, and communication subsystems. From locations across Canada, MDA's global reach and heritage serving international markets with innovative and iconic solutions for space and terrestrial applications is unparalleled. MDA has successfully exported its made-in-Canada solutions for more than four decades, and is poised to capture synergies across its associated companies to expand its capabilities in both traditional and developing markets. MDA is committed to delivering innovation and value in next-generation space exploration, Earth observation, space awareness, and defence systems. The new space economy is based on agility, rapid technology development and harnessing capital to turn commitments into reality, generating benefits for humanity as well as a return on investment. MDA's 1,900 future-focused employees are working together to turn ideas into the products, services, systems, and solutions that make a better world.

ABB (*courtesy Frederic Grandmont*): ABB is a technology leader that is driving the digital transformation of industries. With a history of innovation spanning more than 130 years, ABB has four customer-focused, globally leading businesses: Electrification, Industrial Automation, Motion, and Robotics & Discrete Automation. ABB's Space and Defense Systems section in Quebec city evolved from within the Measurement and Analytics business unit within Industrial Automation. This group specializes in optical sensing and systems, and have contributed to a number of Canadian astronomical instrumentation projects, providing critical elements at all phases from design to manufacturing. For example, ABB is the main industrial sub-contractor for optical systems associated with TMT/NFIRAOS, and ABB was the lead organization behind the CFHT/SITELLE instrument. ABB is also positioned to provide the cryogenic scanning mirror mechanism and laser metrology system of the SPICA satellite proposed to the European Space Agency, in collaboration with the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA), and which includes Canadian astronomers on the science teams. More recently ABB was awarded the WFIRST

CGI EMCCD contract in collaboration with Montreal-based Nuvu Cameras. ABB's instruments have been in space for over 25 years; ABB was the payload prime contractor for the Canadian Science Satellite SCISAT, monitoring atmospheric composition change at unprecedented depth for over 16 years. ABB have also contributed interferometers to the NASA polar orbit weather satellites (JPSS) feeding Canadian weather forecasts since 2011, and interferometers to the Japanese GOSAT 1 and 2 satellites to monitor the steady rise of greenhouse gases around the world. ABB Canada has headquarters in Montreal and more than 4000 employees across Canada, and have been a proud corporate member of CASCA for 15 years.

CHIME Industrial Application (*courtesy Prof. Mark Halpern*): Skaha Remote Sensing Ltd. is a BC company that has developed sensor technology to measure soil moisture remotely over large areas. This technology uses CHIME feeds to measure the water content of soil - in real time (i.e., while watering) - to fine tune the water supply and make irrigation more efficient. This allows growers and agronomists to maximize crop yield and reduce both water and energy usage. This is a leading Canadian technology, and they have customers around the world, especially where water is a valuable resource, such as Australia and BC, among other places.

6 Summary

In this LRP2020 white paper, we identify and summarize the current methods and initiatives used in Canadian astronomy to partner with Canadian industry. These have contributed to Canadian excellence in Astronomy & Astrophysics, led to direct economic benefits in Canada, and provided enriched opportunities for HQP training. We recommend continued *and improved* support for industrial partnerships through NSERC (tri-council), CFI, Mitacs, and other government programs, and we are encouraged that a culture of philanthropy related to astronomical research appears to be growing in Canada. We also encourage Canadian university graduate programs in astronomy to consider adding some professional skills training and/or information for graduate students on the opportunities for astronomical-related research in Canadian industry.

Table 1. Canadian industries with significant roles and partnerships in Canadian astronomical instrumentation.

Name	Location	Projects	Roles
Dynamic Structures (<i>form. Empire</i>)	Vancouver, BC	TMT dome	design
–		MSE dome	design
–		CHIME	mechanical design, pathfinder
MDA (<i>incl. Neptec</i>)	Vancouver, BC	APXS/Mars Rovers	design, fabrication, testing
–		Hitomi/CAMS	design, fabrication, calibration
–		SKA	management, systems engineering
–		SKA	software
–		Colibri X-ray	mission concept study
Sightline Engineering	Vancouver, BC	TMT/NFIRAOS	structural and mechanical design
–		CHIME	outriggers design
Accent Refrigeration Sysys.	Victoria, BC	TMT/NFIRAOS	CO ₂ refrigeration design
Daniels Electronics	Victoria, BC	ALMA Band 3	materials, management
–		ALMA Band 3	mechanical assembly
–		ngVLA	structural and mechanical design
Dorigo Systems	Burnaby, BC	CHIME	low noise amplifiers, filters
–		CHIME	mechanical assembly
Greyback Construction	Penticton, BC	CHIME	telescope construction
–		DRAO, 22 MHz	telescope construction
Quantum Technology	Squamish, BC	TMT/NFIRAOS	refrigeration design
CoolIT	Calgary, AB	CHIME	computing cooling systems
DBSales	Calgary, AB	CHIME	mini-circuits
Blue Sky Spectroscopy	Lethbridge, AB	Herschel/SPIRE	FTS data processing code
–		South Pole Teles.	spectrograph design
–		SPICA/Safari	cryogenics design, test, validation
SED	Saskatoon, SK	ngVLA	Antennas, System Engineering
–		(SKA dishes)	(<i>design not selected</i>)
Magellan	Winnipeg, MB	CASTOR	concept
–		ÉPPÉ	spacecraft conception
Honeywell/COMDEV (<i>incl. Routes</i>)	Cambridge ON	JWST/NIRISS,FGS	design, fabrication, testing
–		Astrosat	UV-detectors, design, fabrication
–		CASTOR	concept, technical
–		Colibri X-ray	mission concept study
–		LiteBIRD	electronics, design, development
Nanowave Technologies	Etobicoke, ON	ALMA Band 3	low noise amplifiers and detectors
FibreTech Optica Ltd.	Kitchener, ON	Gemini/GRACES	design, manufacturing
–		MSE fibre cables	design, manufacturing
AMD	Markham, ON	CHIME	computer processors
–		CHIME	specialized, GPUs
Magellan Aerospace	Mississauga, ON	SCISAT	spacecraft
Microsat Systems Canada (<i>form. Dynacon</i>)	Mississauga, ON	MOST	design, manufacturing
		NEOSSat	design, manufacturing

Continued on next page

Table 1. Canadian astronomy Industry partners – *continued from previous page*

Name	Location	Projects	Roles
–		POEP	design
–		CASSIOPE	spacecraft
–		RADARSAT	spacecraft
Ceravolo Optics	Ottawa, ON	BRITE	design, fabrication
–		MOST	fabrication
Canadensys	Stratford, ON	Lunar Rovers	manufacturing
UTIAS SFL	Toronto, ON	BRITE	manufacturing
ABB	Quebec City, QC	JWST/FGS	design, fabrication, testing
–		JWST/NIRISS	design, fabrication, testing
–		CFHT/SITELLE	design, fabrication, testing
–		TMT/NFIRAOS	design, (<i>fabrication, testing</i>)
–		HITOMI/CAMS	design, fabrication, testing
–		WFIRST/CGI	design, fabrication, testing
–		SPICA/SAFARI	design, fabrication, testing
–		CASTOR	concept studies
–		ÉPPÉ	payload concept
–		TWINKLE	design
INO	Quebec City, QC	TMT/NFIRAOS	design
–		RAVEN	calibration unit
NuVu	Quebec City, QC	WFIRST	readout electronics for coronagraph
OMP	Quebec City, QC	GPI 2.0	opto-mechanical design
–		TMT/NFIRAOS	design
–		NEOSSat	design
TeraXion	Quebec City, QC	ALMA	lasers
MPB Communications	Pointe-Claire, QC	TMT	laser guide stars